

carried out using the same soil salinized with NaCl to make water soluble content 0.8% (EC 6.1 dS/m). The soil also was washed with deionized water to reduce salt content to 0.2% (EC <2.0 dS/m) to check varietal vigor without salt stress. Experimental procedures were the same as for preliminary screening.

All varieties grew normally on the soil whose soluble salt had been mostly washed out with deionized water, but badly on the soil with added NaCl.

Although rice growth was generally inhibited by salt, marked differences in salt tolerance were observed (Table 2). Local hybrid Liuyou 33 was one of the most salt-tolerant varieties, comparable with well-known salt-tolerant Pokkali. Local conventional variety Mafeizhan and breeding line IR36/Meijiangzao 3//Guichao also showed relatively high salt tolerance. Moderate salt tolerance was found in widely used local hybrids Liuyou 63, Shanyou 2, Shanyou 63, and Shanyougui 34.

The validity of these results must be verified under field conditions. ■

Table 2. Damage index of varieties or lines in response to salinity.

Group	Variety or line	Seed source ^a	Damage index (%) ^b	Remarks
1	Liuyou 33	LH	66.7 a	Relatively salt-tolerant
	Pokkali	IR		
2	Mafeizhan	LC	73.3 a	
	IR36/Meijiangzao 3//Guichao	LL		
	Nona Bokra	IR		
	IR29725-22-3-3-3	IR		
3	Liuyou 63	LH	80.0 ab	Intermediate in salt tolerance
	Suomali/Daqu//Hongyangai	LL		
	CSR4	IR		
4	Shanyou 2	LH	86.7 ab	
	Shanyou 63	LH		
	Shanyougui 34	LH		
	IR50	IR		
	IR19085-107-1	IR		
5	Shanyou 30	LH	93.3 b	Salt-sensitive
	Shanyou 64	LH		
	Liuyou 6	LH		
	Guanghuaqinglan Fo	LH		
	Liuyou 437	LH		
	Shuanggui 36	LC		
	Siguiai 44	LC		
	Hongyangai 402/Shuangmei	LL		
	Azaipu/Meifeizao 2//Guichao 2	LL		
	Shuangfei 1/Kezhan	LL		
6	IR36	IR	100 b	
	IR54	IR		
	IR2307-247-2-2-3	IR		
	Qingyouzhi	LC		
	Hongyangai 4/Xinmei 1	LL (CK)		
	Qingraixuan/Meifeizao 2	LL (CK)		

^a LH = local hybrid variety, LC = local conventional variety, LL = local hybrid line, IR = variety or line from IRRI, CK = sensitive check. ^b Statistical analysis done after arc sin change of percentage data. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different. Duncan's test, P = 0.05.

Integrated germplasm improvement – irrigated

Liaogeng 287, a high-yielding rice variety for north China

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Liaogeng 287 fits farmer demands for a high-yielding cultivar with multiple resistance and wide adaptability. It was developed from Quling//Sejiangke/Songqian and released in 1988.

In a 4-yr demonstration 1986-89 in north China, yields were 9.2-9.7 t/ha (see table). Liaogeng 287 matures in 145-160 d and is adapted to the band between 35° and 41° N latitude, where one crop rice and rice - wheat cropping prevail. It is acceptable to farmers in Hebei, Shandong, Beijing, Tianjin, and Liaoning Provinces, where it has been planted on more than 53,000 ha.

It is semidwarf (95 cm tall), erect and nonlodging with dark green foliage. Panicle length is 19 cm; 1,000-grain weight, 25.5 g; seed set, 82.3%; protein content, 6.7%; amylose content, 21.8%; alkali spreading value, low; gel consistency, 74 mm. ■

Performance of Liaogeng 287 in farmers' fields. North China, 1989.

Location	Liaogeng 287		Designation	Local check		Increase over check (%)
	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)		Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	
Suangqiao, Beijing	8.3	145	Jingdao 1	7.2	145	15.5
Dongyeng, Shandong	11.4	142	Zhongguo 91	9.3	145	22.6
Yangge, Tianjin	9.2	146	Jingdao 1	8.1	144	13.4
Yinkou, Liaoning	10.1	160	Liaogeng 5	8.6	160	17.4
Shenyang, Liaoning	9.4	160	Liaogeng 5	8.2	160	13.6

Integrated germplasm improvement – rainfed lowland

Multiple-resistance Ruchi released in Madhya Pradesh, India

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Most of the traditional or improved varieties that farmers cultivate in Madhya Pradesh have little or no pest resistance. Recent epidemics of gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* Wood Mason and bacterial blight (BB) *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* have threatened yield stability.

Newly released variety Ruchi (IET 10449, R269-12-1-1) has high resistance to GM, BB, and blast (Bl) and is tolerant of drought. It was derived from the cross R1924/RP9-4. It is

Yield of Ruchi in All India Coordinated trials, state trials, local verification trials, farmer's field, and maximization demonstrations.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)							
	All India Coordinated Trials				State trials ^e	LVT ^f	Farmer's field ^g	Maximization demonstration ^h
	1986 ^a	1087 ^b	1988 ^c	1989 ^d				
Ruchi	5.2	4.0	4.7	5.2	3.9	6.0	5.2	8.7
Jaya	5.3	3.8	4.4	4.7	3.3	—	—	—
Local check	4.9	3.8	4.5	4.6	3.4	5.3	4.3	—

^a Av over 13 locations. ^b Av over 12 locations ^c Av over 15 locations. ^d Av over 4 locations. ^e Av over 6 yr, 19 trials, 4 locations. ^f Av over 2 yr, 6 locations. ^g Av over 30 farmers' fields of 0.4 ha. ^h Av over 2 yr.

semitall (105 cm ± 10 cm) and, when direct seeded, can compete well with

weeds at the early vegetative phase. Grain yield averages 5-6 t/ha (see table).

Integrated germplasm improvement – upland

Evaluation of early rice genotypes for upland conditions in rolling fields of Karnataka, India

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We evaluated 25 short-duration rice genotypes (<125 d) during rainy season (May-Nov) 1987-89. The area (15°-50' N, 74°-40' E, and 697 m above sea level) has rolling fields that retain moisture for 3 to 3 1/2 mo during the normal cropping season. Annual precipitation averages about 950 mm. Total precipitation during the three cropping seasons of the experiment was 738.0, 1,034.3, and 607.3 mm,

respectively. Soil is a silty clay loam, with pH 6.3, 0.75% organic C, 9 kg P/ha, and 170 kg K/ha.

Rice was drilled in 20-cm rows at 100 kg seed/ha. The crop was fertilized with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

IET7991-11-2 and CR544-1-5 matured about 17 d earlier than high-

It matures in 130 d, is nonlodging even under high fertility because of its thick culms, and suits the rainfed lowland conditions of the state.

Ruchi grain is long, bold 35 g/1,000 grains, and suitable for puffed rice. It registered 4th in All India Coordinated trials in 1986 and first in 1989.

Ruchi may replace medium-duration, high-yielding varieties like IR8, Jaya, Pragati, and Phalguna, and has been recommended for release in 1990. ■

yielding local check Rasi (IET1444) (see table). Neela matured about 10 d earlier. These three genotypes significantly outyielded other early genotypes, and yielded as high as the local check.

In view of their earliness, IET7991-11-2 and Neela have been recommended for multilocation trials. CR544-1-5 was not considered because its grain tends to shatter when harvest is delayed. ■

Grain yield and plant characters^a of a few early rice genotypes under rainfed conditions in Mugad, Karnataka, India.

Genotype	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Duration (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)
IET7991-11-2	74.1	17.9	321.5	101	3.7
CR544-1-5	74.9	19.7	241.5	102	3.3
Neela	62.0	20.2	307.3	108	3.2
Rasi (IET1444) (local check)	79.7	18.2	250.0	118	3.1
LSD (0.05)	7.1	7.8	75.5	4.0	0.9
CV (%)	6.1	20.0	11.3	3.1	1.5

^aAv of 1987, 1988, and 1989 rainy seasons.

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Fertilizer management

Impact of nursery nutrients on growth and yield of rice crop

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Nursery management is an important factor in crop production. In very thickly populated nurseries, plant roots spread

out on the soil surface and intensively exploit soil fertility. If soil fertility is low, seedlings will be thin and pale. A considerable amount of the nursery may be spoiled during pulling.

We studied the use of N and P by the rice nursery and the impact of nursery nutrition on the subsequent crop in a field experiment at Saraimiara farm. Soil of the experimental field was sandy loam,

Table 1. Effect of fertilizer applied to nursery on growth parameters of 25-d-old rice seedlings.^a

Seedling treatment	Leaves/plant (no.)	Height (cm)	100-seedling weight (g)	N content (%)	P content (%)
No N	3.8	19.2	65	1.86	0.251
100 kg N/ha	4.7	30.4	152	2.28	0.258
200 kg N/ha	5.1	31.9	243	2.34	0.312
No P	4.8	30.8	141	2.08	0.323
21.5 kg P/ha	5.0	31.3	153	2.12	0.338
43.0 kg P/ha	5.3	31.7	166	2.15	0.345
LSD (0.05)	0.3	1.01	20	0.04	0.005

^a 2 yr pooled data.